

PREVENT INFECTIOUS AND NON-INFECTIOUS DISEASES OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Gastrointestinal diseases are a type of disease associated with the gastrointestinal tract, that is, the esophagus, stomach, small intestine, large intestine and rectum, and the auxiliary organs of digestion, the liver, gallbladder and pancreas. Gastrointestinal diseases are diseases that affect the stomach. Today, 3-6 million children worldwide die every year from infectious gastroenteritis. Although most of these diseases are not very dangerous, their complications and secondary symptoms lead to serious consequences. Intestinal infections are one of the most pressing problems in the world today..

Relevance: Gastrointestinal diseases are a type of disease associated with the gastrointestinal tract, that is, the esophagus, stomach, small intestine, large intestine and rectum, and the auxiliary organs of digestion, the liver, gallbladder and pancreas. Gastrointestinal diseases are diseases that affect the stomach. Today, 3-6 million children worldwide die every year from infectious gastroenteritis. Although most of these diseases are not very dangerous, their complications and secondary symptoms lead to serious consequences. Intestinal infections are one of the most pressing problems in the world today.

The goal of our research is to learn about the types of gastrointestinal infections and to study measures aimed at preventing infectious and non-infectious diseases.

Methods and Materials. Gastrointestinal infections are viral, bacterial, or parasitic infections that cause gastroenteritis, which is inflammation of the gastrointestinal tract, including the stomach and small intestine. Symptoms include vomiting, diarrhea, and abdominal pain. Dehydration is a major risk of gastrointestinal infections, so dehydration is important, but most GI infections are self-limiting and resolve within a few days.

Diagnosis. If symptoms are suspected to be those of a gastrointestinal infection, the diagnosis can be confirmed by laboratory tests such as a stool sample culture test or antigen test. In some cases (e.g., E. coli, Salmonella, Clostridium difficile infection), bacterial resistance (if present) can be determined by antibiotic susceptibility testing to guide antibiotic therapy.

Conclusion: Infectious and non-infectious diseases of the gastrointestinal tract are increasing day by day, and new strains of pathogens are emerging. Considering that these diseases mainly occur in young children, it is important for every parent to be attentive to their children and follow the rules of personal hygiene. The most correct way is to visit a doctor when the first symptoms of the disease are noticed. It is important to be attentive to food products, which are the most common source of the disease, namely: keeping them clean,

washing them thoroughly, paying special attention to the quality of the product and the expiration date .

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